

**THE FORMATION OF A PERSONALITY THROUGH THE PRESS OF
PEDAGOGICAL AND CULTURAL REALITY**

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Abstract: This scientific article is intended to analyze the main elements of the formation of a person’s personality; in addition, it reveals such concepts as: personality, person, individual, individuality. This article examines in detail the fundamental concepts of personal development, and also identifies the factors and driving forces of personal development.

Key words: personality, personality development, personality formation, education, individuality, factors of personality development.

Introduction

For a long time there have been debates about what is more important for the development of personality - the biological nature of a person, society or human culture.

This contrast is mainly represented by the psychology of human nature, represented mainly by Carl Rogers. According to Rogers, human biology tends to develop and evolve in the same way that plant species develop and evolve. Human biological nature tends to be positive, constructive, mature and sociable.

The term “personal development” has two meanings: 1) as development, its processes and results, and 2) as intentional care (coercion, formation, shaping, designing, shaping, etc.)

Main part

The development of the personality culture of a modern teenager is based on a combination of socio-psychological and pedagogical activities. The culture of support and assistance to children is based on a specific methodology that guarantees the quality of modern education. Psychological and pedagogical support needs to combine science and practice with a certain methodology into a unified system of its components - scientific, applied, practical and organizational aspects.

To solve this problem and overcome the crisis, society needs development to form a culture of personality, and the level of culture of dignity should become the main goal of state cultural policy [4].

The main goal of education is the formation of personality, its comprehensive and concise development. However, in order to successfully solve this problem, it is necessary to know what personality is, how its development occurs and what

factors influence its formation. Problems of personality development are actively being developed in philosophy, general and social psychology and other sciences. But this does not exclude the need its research in pedagogy. A lot of vital information on these issues is contained in the works of J. A. Komensky, A. Disterweg, K.D. Ushinsky, P.P. Blonsky, A.S. Makarenko, S.T. Shatsky, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, etc. Essential for pedagogy is, first of all, an understanding of the very concept of personality. In fact, what is personality and what is the relationship between this concept and its related concept, man?

Famous philosopher V.P. Tugalinov said that the most important characteristics of a person are:

- 1) Be rational,
- 2) Responsibility,
- 3) freedom
- 4) Responsibility,
- 5) Individuality.

Important characteristics of a person's personality are his social activity, integrity and stability of his moral views and beliefs. This, in particular, is activity in work and upholding one's ideological and moral principles.

Conclusion

The result of the influence of all these factors is the process of socialization of the individual - assimilation and active education, depending on the activity and internal position of the individual in relation to environmental and educational influences, the personality can be formed in different directions. If the student has a negative attitude towards these influences, then he will develop in the direction opposite to that towards which the teacher is oriented. Therefore, B should positively influence the internal stimulus of the individual's self-improvement activities. It is this activity and the desire of a developing person for personal perfection that ultimately determines his development.

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